

Research Article

Assessing forest fire vulnerability using artificial neural networks in Almora district, Uttarakhand, India

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Abstract

Forests are vital to terrestrial ecosystems and they offer essential services for climate regulation and human welfare. However, the increasing trend in forest fires poses a significant threat to these ecosystems. This study aims to map and assess forest fire vulnerability zones within Almora district, Uttarakhand, India, using geospatial technologies and the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) technique. Twelve environmental indicators related to forest fire vulnerability, including elevation, slope, land use/land cover (LULC), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Vegetation Health Index (VHI), temperature, precipitation, humidity, wind speed, Land Surface Temperature (LST), and distance from settlements and roads, were considered. The study revealed that a strip running from northern to southern Almora, including Someshwar, Dwarahat, and Ranikhet, is highly vulnerable to forest fires. This region is characterized by moderate to high elevation, a moderate to steep slope, and well-connected roads and settlements, particularly in Dwarahat and Ranikhet tehsils. The central and southern parts of Almora also exhibit good road connectivity, dense human settlements, and receive moderate to low precipitation, all of which contribute to a higher fire risk. In contrast, the eastern and western parts of Almora, comprising northern Sult, northern Bhikiyasain, and Banoli tehsils, are significantly less vulnerable to forest fires. These areas have moderate slopes, low to moderate elevation, higher precipitation in the eastern parts, and lower precipitation in the western parts, making them comparatively less prone to fire incidents. Validation through the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve confirmed the accuracy of the model, with an 82% area under the curve.

Key words: Geospatial technique, LST, LULC, ROC

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1. Introduction

Forests play a crucial role in terrestrial ecosystems, which offer numerous ecosystem services vital for climate regulation and human welfare (Sturrock et al. 2011; Malhi et al. 2020; Youcef et al. 2020; Ren et al. 2022). Among various natural disturbances, forest fires pose a significant challenge. Due to rising global temperatures, population growth, and more human activity in forested areas, the frequency of forest fires has increased (Preston et al. 2009). Forests have the capacity to withstand certain environmental alterations, despite their

capacity to increase forest fire damage and vulnerability to environmental alterations. Forest fires not only contribute significantly to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions but also have profound adverse effects on wildlife, ecosystems, and watershed management (Mishra et al. 2023). They constitute disasters with substantial environmental and ecological impacts that pose threats to both human lives and livelihoods. From 2001 to 2018, approximately 7.2 billion hectares of land, including forests, other wooded lands, and other areas, succumbed to wildfires globally, averaging around 400 million hectares annually (Robinne 2021). Although the annual burned area between 2013 and 2018 was lower than the long-term average (FAO 2020), research indicates a decline of $24.3 \pm 8.8\%$ in global burned areas over the past 18 years (Andela et al. 2017). However, a re-evaluation of climate model ensembles suggests that despite this decline, forest fire risk has increased by approximately 1.1 times in current climate conditions compared to pre-industrial times, and under future climate scenarios, such as a 2°C global temperature increase, it could double (Aponte et al. 2016). Forest fires have been a recurring issue in Uttarakhand, India, causing significant damage to the region's forest cover and biodiversity. Studies have shown that forest fires in Uttarakhand have led to substantial destruction, with large areas of forest cover being completely burned during fire incidents (Mina et al. 2023). The severity of forest fires in the region is evident from incidents where fires spread across multiple districts, impacting a significant portion of the state's forests (Suresh Babu et al. 2018). Since the 1970s, geospatial technology has played an important role in studying the impacts of forest fire emissions. This technology has revolutionized the ability to detect active forest fire locations or fire points (Rostami et al. 2022), map burnt forest areas (Giglio et al. 2018; Ertugrul et al. 2019) and assess forest fire danger (Ertugrul et al. 2021). Among the key instruments in this field are two multispectral imaging sensors: the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS). Both have proven highly effective in detecting active fires, with VIIRS particularly adept at identifying smaller fires due to their global coverage and high spatial resolution, surpassing the capabilities of MODIS in this regard (Schroeder et al. 2014). The primary aim of this study is to delineate the forest fire vulnerability zones within the Almora district of Uttarakhand, India, employing the Artificial Neural Network technique. To achieve this objective, comprehensive forest fire data for the year 2022 sourced from FIRMS (2025) were utilized, along with twelve distinct environmental indicators related to forest fire vulnerability. These indicators are prepared from the Landsat 8 dataset using ArcGIS 10.8.2 software, and a land use and land cover map is prepared from Sentinel-2 satellite data.

2. Study area and data source

2.1. Study area

Almora district (Fig. 1) is situated within the Kumaon division of Uttarakhand state, India, and lies in the lesser Himalayan terrain. Geographically, the study area spans from 29°57' to 29°61'N and 79°63' to 79°67'E, covering approximately 3,144 km² and is characterized by its hilly and rugged terrain. The ele-

vation in the district ranges from about 800 to over 2,757 m a.s.l., with Almora town serving as the district headquarters. The district forms part of the Lesser Himalayas and features a network of rivers such as the Kosi, Suyal, Ramganga, and Gagas, which contribute to the Ganga River system.

Almora experiences a subtropical highland climate (Köppen Cwb), with pleasant summers and cold winters. The average annual temperature ranges between 17°C and 19°C, with summer temperatures typically between 20°C and 28°C, and winter temperatures dropping to between 5°C and 15°C. The district receives an average annual precipitation of about 1,100 to 1,300 mm, primarily during the monsoon months from June to September. The vegetation in Almora varies with altitude and is representative of the Himalayan moist temperate zone. At lower elevations (800–1,200 m), subtropical pine forests, dominated by chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*), are common. Mid-elevation zones (1,200–1,800 m) feature mixed broadleaf forests, including species like oak (*Quercus leucotrichophora*), rhododendron, and *Myrica*. At higher elevations (above 1,800 m), temperate forests of deodar (*Cedrus deodara*), fir, spruce, and Himalayan cypress are found. The Binsar Wildlife Sanctuary, located in this zone, supports rich biodiversity, including leopards, barking deer, and over 200 bird species. Overall, Almora district is a significant ecological and cultural region of Uttarakhand, with diverse vegetation, varied physiographic features, and a climate that supports both biodiversity and agriculture, while also posing several environmental challenges.

Figure 1. Study area.

2.2. Data source and preparation

To generate the forest fire vulnerability map of the study area, 12 environmental indicators related to forest fire vulnerability were used: elevation, slope, land use/land cover (LULC), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Vegetation Health Index (VHI), temperature, precipitation, humidity, wind speed, Land Surface Temperature (LST), and distances from settlements and roads (Table 1). Data were sourced from high-quality repositories such as the USGS Earth Explorer (2022) for elevation, slope, NDVI, VHI, and LST, and the LULC map was taken from the Sentinel-2 satellite. Apart from that, meteorological data is taken from NASA POWER. The elevation and slope data were derived from SRTM DEM (USGS Earth Explorer 2022) with a spatial resolution of 30 x 30 m. LULC map has been clipped from Sentinel-2 satellite data as this satellite has high spatial resolution (10 m) data, and NDVI were processed from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS images formula given by (Mohanasundaram et al. 2023) using various spectral bands to classify land cover and assess vegetation health respectively. VHI and LST utilized thermal and near-infrared data to evaluate vegetation stress and surface temperatures. Meteorological factors were compiled from historical climate data to understand patterns affecting fire behavior. The street map is taken from the OpenStreetMap (OSM 2025) database, and settlement density was digitized manually from Google Earth (2025). Active fire data from NASA's FIRMS (FIRMS 2025) were used to validate the study.

Table 1. Data source of different environmental indicators related to forest fire vulnerability factors used in this study.

Data layer	Source data	Spatial resolution
LULC	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS (USGS Earth Explorer 2022)	30 x 30 m
Distance from road	OpenStreetMap (OSM 2025)	-
Settlement	Google Earth (2025)	-
VHI	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS (USGS Earth Explorer 2022)	30 x 30 m and 100 x 100 m
Wind speed, temperature, humidity	NASA POWER (2025)	-
Precipitation	Indian Meteorological Department (IMD 2025)	-
LST	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS (USGS Earth Explorer 2022)	100 x 100 m
NDVI	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS (USGS Earth Explorer 2022)	30 x 30 m
Elevation, slope	SRTM DEM (USGS Earth Explorer 2022)	30 x 30 m
Fire points	NASA's Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) (NASA FIRMS 2025)	NRT VIIRS 375 m Active Fire product

3. Methodology

3.1. Artificial Neural Networks

The Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) method is widely recognized as one of the most popular machine learning techniques for identifying areas susceptible to forest fires (De Souza et al. 2015). ANN techniques rely on connectionist systems that emulate biological neural networks, enabling the parallel processing of vast quantities of interconnected cells. These techniques mimic the functioning of the human brain, effectively addressing complex nonlinear problems with

numerous variables and components. Additionally, they can detect patterns and discern trends in intricate issues (Jafari Goldarag et al. 2016; Gorsevski et al. 2016). Neural network becomes highly useful in situations where making a traditional algorithm is very complex, and when recognizing patterns in the data is very important. Rather than when it is programmed for certain work, these neural networks learned through examples. A neural network is also flexible to imperfect inputs and incomplete data and well fitted for correcting these incomplete data. After training, a neural network can perform rapid prediction very efficiently. ANN are widely used in various fields such as control system, pattern recognition, forecasting and optimization. ANN's performance is fluctuating across different studies. In some cases, it demonstrates excellent performance, such as in the study of forest fire susceptibility in India, where ANN achieved a high receiver operating characteristic (ROC)/area under the ROC curve (AUC) score of 0.903 (Sharma et al. 2022). Interestingly, the effectiveness of ANN seems to depend on the specific context and dataset used. For instance, in the study conducted in Türkiye, random forest machine learning techniques outperformed ANN significantly (Purnama et al. 2024). However, in the Indian context, ANN was among the top-performing models (Sharma et al. 2022). This suggests that the performance of ANN may be influenced by regional factors and the nature of the input data. In this study as depicted in (Fig. 2), an ANN model was constructed to forecast forest fires, using a multilayer perceptron architecture and trained with the backpropagation algorithm. The feed-forward network comprised an input layer with 12 neurons (representing conditioning factors), a hidden layer, and an output layer.

Figure 2. Methodological flowchart of the study.

3.2. Neural network training and performance

The schematic diagram of the architecture of the neural network designed for this study is shown in Fig. 3. The selected input features include monthly averages of wind speed, relative humidity, and temperature, along with LULC, NDVI, VHI, LST, elevation, slope, precipitation, road density, and settlement distribution. The network's output result is the forest fire vulnerability index. A feedforward neural network utilizing the backpropagation algorithm was built using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 16.0 (SPSS) software to generate a forest fire vulnerability map, and the training was conducted in batch mode, as outlined (Mahmood and Merza 2013).

Figure 3. Artificial neural networks architecture.

3.3. Accuracy assessment

To evaluate the accuracy of the forest fire vulnerability model, a dataset consisting of 225 fire instances from NASA's FIRMS for the year 2022 was used. The dataset was divided into training and testing subsets on the basis of random selection, with 700 instances used for training the model and the remaining 300 instances designated for testing its predictive capabilities. The performance of the model was assessed using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, a powerful tool for visualizing and evaluating classifier output quality (Chen et al. 2018; Pal and Chowdhuri 2019). The ROC curve plots the true positive rate (sensitivity) against the false positive rate (1 - specificity) at various threshold settings. The closer the ROC curve is to the upper left corner of the graph, the higher the overall accuracy of the model.

3.4. Environmental indicators related to forest fire vulnerability

The development of a forest fire vulnerability map is a critical endeavor, depending on the meticulous selection of various factors that collectively contribute to its accuracy and reliability. In this study, a comprehensive array of factors has been thoughtfully considered to craft a holistic view of the landscape's susceptibility to forest fires. For this assessment, twelve factors were taken. These twelve factors have been prepared from Landsat 8 data that was downloaded from the USGS data source (USGS Earth Explorer 2022), and then processing has been done on these satellite images. The precipitation data is taken from the Indian Meteorological Department (IMD 2025); humidity, wind, and temperature data are taken from the NASA POWER repository (NASA POWER 2025). Each of these factors plays a unique role in the overall vulnerability assessment, and their amalgamation promises a robust and informed forest fire vulnerability map. Pictorial representation of each of the factors that affect forest fire is given in Fig. 4.

3.4.1. Slope

Slope angle is a critical factor that exerts a profound influence on the dynamics of terrain and the movement of objects across the Earth's surface. In the context of forest fires, it plays a pivotal role in determining the speed and pattern of fire spread (Grace and Keeley 2006). Essentially, the degree of slope acts as a guiding force for fire propagation; it facilitates the rapid uphill movement of fires while hindering their progress when descending (Kushla and Ripple 1997). To understand and analyze the role of slope angle in the context of forest fire behavior (Kushla and Ripple 1997) frequently utilize a slope map of the study area, which is generated from a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). This map is then divided into distinct slope categories, namely: 0–12°, 12–19.9°, 19.9–27.5°, 27.5–36°, and 36–73.8° (Castro and Chuvieco 1998). The slope of the terrain is a critical factor in shaping fire behavior. Steeper slopes can accelerate the spread of fire due to the alignment of fuels and the flow of air, creating conditions conducive to rapid combustion.

3.4.2. Elevation

The climate of a region is intricately linked to its altitude, a relationship that is strongly correlated (Aniya 1985). Different elevations within a geographic area exhibit distinct climatic conditions, which, in turn, have a profound influence on the local flora and geological characteristics. This interconnectedness is of particular significance in the context of mapping forest fire vulnerability (Fernández and Lutz 2010). The topography of the land, including elevation and slope, plays an equally significant role. To better comprehend the interplay of these factors, the study employed SRTM DEM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Digital Elevation Model) (USGS Earth Explorer 2022) data to create an altitude map of the study area. This map was then divided into five distinct altitudinal zones using the natural break method, as this method minimizes within class variation and maximizes between class variation.

3.4.3. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

The NDVI is a widely used remote sensing technique to assess the health of vegetation over a specific area (Zhanguzhina et al. 2025). NDVI is calculated using data from Landsat 8 OLI satellite and can help monitor changes in vegetation cover, detect drought stress, and assess overall land cover changes (Schloss et al. 1999).

NDVI is computed using ArcGIS 10.8.2 software with the help of the following formula (Mohanasundaram et al. 2023) (eq. 1–3).

$$\text{NDVI} = (\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Red}) \text{ (eq. 1)}$$

Where:

NIR is the reflectance value in the near-infrared band.

Red is the reflectance value in the red band.

$$\text{For Landsat 8: NDVI} = (\text{B5} - \text{B4}) / (\text{B5} + \text{B4}) \text{ (eq. 2)}$$

$$\text{For Landsat 7: NDVI} = (\text{B4} - \text{B3}) / (\text{B4} + \text{B3}) \text{ (eq. 3)}$$

The resulting NDVI values typically range from -1 to $+1$, with higher values indicating healthier and denser vegetation. Negative values often represent non-vegetated surfaces (e.g., water or barren land), while values close to zero can indicate sparse or stressed vegetation.

3.4.4. Land Surface Temperature

LST holds a pivotal role in the analysis of forest fire susceptibility, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the environmental dynamics that influence fire risk. LST is a multifaceted parameter with far-reaching implications, extending beyond its direct involvement in forest fire assessments. This parameter plays a central role in various ecological models, ranging from digital weather forecasting to drought indices, climatic diversity assessments, and the determination of energy and water cycling within the Earth's atmosphere, as discussed by Van Leeuwen et al. (2011). In this study, the acquisition of an LST map was accomplished through the application of the mono-window algorithm method, an approach pioneered by Jiang and Tian (2010). This method, acknowledged for its effectiveness in calculating LST from remote sensing data, serves as a critical component in the study's analytical framework. By utilizing Landsat 8 satellite data acquired on April 12, 2022, and concurrent meteorological data, including temperature and humidity, obtained from the Directorate of Meteorology (IMD 2025), the research was able to derive a precise LST map.

3.4.5. Vegetation Health Index

Peng et al. (2014) undergoes into the intricate interplay between temperature variability and vegetation activity, employing NDVI as a surrogate for their analysis. Likewise, De Jong et al. (2011) conducted an in-depth exploration of the monotonic trends in greening and browning, utilizing global NDVI time-series

data. However, it is crucial to recognize that NDVI measurements possess a relative weakness when it comes to capturing short-term fluctuations, particularly those influenced by weather-related factors. Distinguishing these transient signals, such as those brought about by weather anomalies like droughts, from the cumulative, long-term ecological impacts can be a daunting task (Kogan 1995). To tackle this inherent challenge, the scientific community introduced the Vegetation Condition Index (VCI) as an innovative solution. The VCI's primary purpose is to segregate the signals originating from weather-related influences from those driven by ecological factors within the NDVI data (Kogan and Sullivan 1993). Moreover, in an attempt to discern the effects of excessive moisture from those of droughts, the VHI was conceived. The VHI is designed to monitor meteorological droughts by combining the VCI with the heat status of the vegetation canopy, an approach initially proposed by Kogan (1995). Thus, the VHI is derived from a combination of VCI and Temperature Condition Index (TCI), considering both vegetation cover and temperature effects on vegetation health. The formulation of VHI is as follows (Mohanasundaram et al. 2023) (eq. 4):

$$VHI = [\alpha]VCI + [1 - \alpha]TCI \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

Where:

VCI is the Vegetation Condition Index

TCI is the Temperature Condition Index

$\alpha = 0.5$ weightage was assigned to both VCI and TCI, with both factors represented by a value of 0.5. This signifies that both VCI and TCI equally contribute to the assessment of vegetation health in the region.

The distribution of the VHI in Almora district provides crucial information for forest fire risk assessment and management. It highlights the areas that require immediate attention in terms of fire prevention, such as those falling under the "very low" and "low" categories. Simultaneously, regions with "high" and "very high". VHI classifications offer potential natural safeguards against forest fires. Understanding these dynamics is very important for effective fire prevention, control, and recovery strategies to protect the district's ecosystems, human communities, and natural resources.

3.4.6. Land use/land cover map

A LULC map was generated using Sentinel-2 satellite data specifically acquired for the study area in April 2022. The LULC analysis of Almora district has been done with ArcGIS 10.8.2, revealing six prominent features that define the landscape: water bodies, dense vegetation, agricultural land, built-up areas, barren land, and sparse vegetation. Almora's land cover in 2022 reveals valuable insights for forest fire risk assessment. Dense forests (49.18%), while crucial for the environment, pose a high risk if dry. Sparse vegetation (45.79%) also carries potential fire risk, especially during dry periods. Water bodies (0.24%) act as natural firebreaks, but surrounding areas still need management and preventive measures. Though less susceptible, built-up areas (3.58%) and agricultural land (1.07%) can be affected by fires in nearby forests. Understanding this composition is crucial for developing targeted fire prevention and mitigation strategies.

3.4.7. Distance from road

Street data for the study area is prepared from OpenStreetMap. Forest fires are a complex ecological challenge, with the potential to originate from both natural and human sources. In the case of human-induced fires, road networks play a crucial role. Roads, whether used for vehicle transportation or other human-related activities, create an expansive interface with forested areas, and this interface can significantly elevate the risk of fires (Tien Bui et al. 2018). Specifically, regions of forests in close proximity to roads tend to exhibit a higher susceptibility to forest fires. This is primarily attributed to the increased human presence and activities in these areas. In light of these considerations, a basic approach is to establish buffer zones along road networks within forested regions. The creation of buffer zones at regular intervals, such as 500 meters, offers a structured means of investigating the influence of roads on forest fire vulnerability.

3.4.8. Distance from settlement

The collection of settlement data has been done from Google Earth Engine (Google Earth 2025), wherein settlements are digitized in KML format and subsequently converted into a raster layer compatible with ArcGIS 10.8.2. A proactive strategy is used to understand the settlement relation with forest fires. This strategy involves the creation of buffer zones at regular 500-meter intervals from the settlements within the study area. These buffer zones serve as a structured means of researching the influence of settlements on forest fire risk (Tien Bui et al. 2018).

3.4.9. Local climate factor

In the context of forest fire research, the consideration of meteorological factors is of paramount importance when it comes to predicting and mapping forest fire vulnerability zones. Among these meteorological factors, several key variables stand out as vital contributors to these efforts, including monthly mean precipitation, monthly mean relative humidity, monthly mean temperatures, and wind speed (Tien Bui et al. 2018). These factors collectively provide critical insights into the environmental conditions that influence the likelihood and severity of forest fires. In this study, data for April were sourced from NASA's database, specifically the NASA POWER dataset (NASA POWER 2025). A strategic approach was adopted to download meteorological data from the NASA POWER data source, for which 50-point data was taken from Almora and surrounding districts so that Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation techniques can easily be carried out to get a raster map of wind speed, humidity and temperature, on a district level. This dataset provides valuable meteorological information, including temperature, precipitation, and relative humidity, on a district level. With this data in hand, IDW interpolation techniques in ArcGIS 10.8.2 were employed to create spatial representations of all meteorological variables. Interpolation allows researchers to estimate values for specific locations based on data from nearby points, enabling the creation of detailed maps that can be used to identify forest fire vulnerable zones.

Figure 4. Environmental indicators related to forest fire vulnerability. A elevation (m a.s.l.) B humidity (gm/kg) C settlements D NDVI E LST F Precipitation (mm) G LULC (2022) H road I wind speed (m/sec) J slope K temperature (°C) L VHI.

3.4.9.1. Monthly mean temperature (April)

Temperature, a prominent meteorological factor, has a substantial influence on the occurrence and dynamics of forest fires in this region. As this place is characterised by lush greenery, the relationship between temperature and forest fires is complicated. During the dry and hot seasons, notably in late spring and summer, rising temperatures render the region more susceptible to forest fires. The intense heat can lead to the dryness of vegetation, causing it to lose crucial moisture and become increasingly prone to ignition. Whether ignited by human activities or lightning strikes, the likelihood of fires starting in these conditions is notably increased.

3.4.9.2. Monthly mean precipitation (April)

Precipitation data has been downloaded from the India Meteorological Department for the month of April, and the monthly mean rainfall has been prepared from this data. April has been selected for the analysis of forest fire, as this month is very susceptible to forest fire, and this month is a transition between the end of winter and the beginning of summer. To transform the collected precipitation data into a meaningful precipitation map, the IDW algorithm, a Geographical Information System (GIS) operation, was employed. This method was employed to interpolate precipitation values across the entire region, as it provides a comprehensive visualization of precipitation patterns within the Almora district.

3.4.9.3. Monthly mean relative humidity (April)

To opt the mean relative humidity of the study area, 50 points have been taken in the same way as taken as discussed above from the NASA POWER dataset, and IDW techniques are applied on this data to convert it into a map that illustrates the distribution of relative humidity in Almora district during April. This map serves as a critical tool for forest management authorities and this research. It offers a clear and informative depiction of the relative humidity patterns within the Almora district during the month when forest fires are most prevalent.

3.4.9.4. Monthly mean wind speed (April)

The primary focus was to acquire precise wind speed data, a crucial parameter in assessing forest fire risk and behavior (Tien Bui et al. 2018). The wind data is sourced from the NASA POWER Data Portal (NASA POWER 2025), with a specific focus on Almora, a region known for its vulnerability to forest fires. To transform the collected data into meaningful insights, an IDW GIS operation was conducted. This operation was utilized to interpolate wind speed values across the entire region, facilitating the creation of a wind speed map.

4. Results

4.1. Artificial Neural Network output

Forest fires have adverse impacts influenced by various factors, and the effects of these factors can differ from place to place. In this study, 12 factors were considered to ensure the inclusion of important factors in assessing forest fire vulnerability in the study area. Fig. 5 shows the forest fire vulnerability map of the study area, generated by using an ANN method, and classified the area into very low, low, moderate, high, and very high forest fire vulnerability zones.

Figure 5. Forest fire vulnerability zone of the study area.

The map shows that the five classified zones are unevenly distributed across the study area, with the very high forest fire vulnerability zone concentrated in the northern and southern parts. This northern region, where the very high vulnerability zone is concentrated, features high elevation, moderate to low temperature, low humidity, moderate precipitation and low wind speed, road connectivity, and settlement density. In the southern region of Almora, forest fire vulnerability is also very high, as it has high elevation and high slope that contributes rapid spread of fire, and also it has high temperature that additionally adds to form a conducive environment for fire to occur. The high vulnerability in this zone can be attributed to its high elevation high slope. Because these

factors lead to reduced human interference, which allows dry leaves and other combustible materials to accumulate, which serve as fuel for fires. Thus, even though the climatic conditions might suggest moderate fire risk, the accumulation of dry materials due to a lack of human activity makes this zone highly susceptible to forest fires.

Table 2. Forest fire vulnerability.

Vulnerability class	Area (km ²)	Area (%)
Very low	238.3	7.68
Low	501	16.16
Moderate	851.9	27.47
Very high	1,033.2	33.31
High very high	476.4	15.36

The northwestern, eastern and south eastern part of the study area features very low and low forest vulnerability to forest fire. Table 2 presents the area and percentage-wise distribution of forest fires in the five classified zones of forest fire vulnerability. The very high vulnerable zone covers the maximum area (1033.2 Km²), which is 33.31% of the total area and the very low vulnerable zone covers only (238.3 Km²), which is 7.68% of the total area.

4.2. Validation of the Artificial Neural Network model

The ROC curve is a graphical tool used to evaluate the performance of a classification model or diagnostic test. It plots the true positive rate (also known as sensitivity, calculated as $TP / (TP + FN)$) on the vertical axis against the false positive rate (which is 1 minus specificity, calculated as $FP / (FP + TN)$) on the horizontal axis (Nykänen et al. 2015). The area under the ROC curve (AUC) provides a single value summary of the model's accuracy. An AUC of 1.0 reflects a model with perfect prediction capability, achieving maximum sensitivity and minimum false positives ($1 - \text{specificity} = 0$). In contrast, an AUC of 0.5 represents a model that performs no better than random chance, and its ROC curve would lie along the diagonal line. In this study, the ROC curve and AUC were computed using SPSS software to assess the predictive performance of the spatial model. To verify the accuracy of the machine learning model's predictions, geotagged pictures of 32 forest fire sites that had been clicked during the field survey that was compared with NASA FIRMS (2025) forest fire inventory data. The comparison revealed that 28 out of the 32 surveyed sites matched the data from NASA FIRMS, confirming the reliability of the NASA FIRMS inventory data. Further, the success of the vulnerability assessment of the model was examined through the ROC curve. Therefore, in order to validate the result of the model, a validation process based on the 1000 fire points was considered, of which 700 points were considered for testing and 300 for validation of the model. According to Nykänen et al. (2015), the result of the curve is considered to be excellent (>0.9), accepted ($0.8-0.9$), good ($0.7-0.8$), and

Figure 6. Receiver operating characteristic validation of the ANN model.

considerable (0.5–0.7). The result of the ROC (Fig. 6) shows that 0.82 of the area under the curve, which validates that the study has an acceptable result.

5. Discussion

The development of a forest fire vulnerability map is a critical endeavor, depending on the meticulous selection of various factors that collectively contribute to its accuracy and reliability. In this study, a comprehensive array of factors has been thoughtfully considered to craft a holistic view of the landscape's susceptibility to forest fires. Each of these factors plays a unique role in the overall vulnerability assessment, and their amalgamation promises a robust and informed forest fire vulnerability map. LULC plays a foundational component in predicting forest fire vulnerability. The study region, Almora, has 45% of the total area under sparse tree and 49% under tree cover, which means more than 90% of the total area comes under tree cover that make this area highly susceptible to forest fire.

Slope is another factor that has been taken care of in the research area; more than 50% of the total geographical area has a slope of more than 20°, which spreads the forest fire by rolling down the fire-caught pine fruit. The elevation of this region also plays an important role in forest fire vulnerability. It has been found that area that has both high elevation and a high degree of slope is more vulnerable to forest fire. For example, the northern part of Someswar tehsil, Northern Ranikhet, and the middle Dwarahat have higher elevation and slope as well, which makes this area highly vulnerable to forest fires. The NDVI provides insights into the greenness of vegetation, shedding light on fuel load and the potential for fire ignition. Approximately 70% of the total geographical area has moderate to very low NDVI, which means a major portion of the area has available fuel load for fire to ignite. Another factor, land surface temperature, is indicative of the surface's heat, which is closely related to ignition point and fire behavior, which means that the lower the LST, the cooler the area is and vice versa. In the research region, approximately 30% of the total geographical area

has moderate to high LST. Vegetation health index captured the short-term variations in the health of vegetation, as NDVI gives the long-term trend of vegetation, so to capture the short-term variation, vegetation health is calculated, and it was found that 35% of the total geographical area has low VHI.

The consideration of meteorological factors is also important when it comes to predicting and mapping forest fire vulnerability zones. Among these meteorological factors, several key variables stand out as vital contributors to this event, including monthly mean precipitation, monthly mean relative humidity, monthly mean temperatures, and wind speed. As far as raster data of the study area is concerned, approximately 50% of the total geographical area has a high humidity and temperature zone. Out of the total geographical area, 70% experienced high wind speed, which is another crucial concern about forest fires. The eastern part of the Almora district has relatively high rainfall, in comparison to the western part zone, which is another significant attribute to forest fire.

Another factor that affects forest fire is the human-induced factor, which is the distance from roads and the distance from settlements. It has been observed that human-induced factor is to some extent related to forest fire, because the northern part of the research region has very high vulnerability to forest fire, but it is also less inhabited by humans, and has very low road density. Perhaps due to the higher accumulation of fuel wood and less interference, fire spread easily and unnoticeably. However, the other area of Almora that includes Chaukhutiya, Dwarahat and Ranikhet tehsil, is highly vulnerable to forest fire. One of the major contributors to high vulnerability is the well-connected road network and the appropriate number of settlement patches that make it vulnerable to human-induced forest fire.

6. Conclusion

Mapping and assessing forest fire vulnerability is crucial because forest fires pose a serious threat to the ecosystem. In this context, geospatial technologies have proven to be effective tools in mitigating the vulnerabilities posed by forest fires. As discussed in the results section, forest fire vulnerability varies from region to region, influenced by various conditioning factors. Higher elevation, low road density, and low settlement density are associated with a lower likelihood of fire occurrence (Ertugrul et al. 2019). In this research, it has been found that elevation and slope play a major role. The area with a high degree of slope and high elevation has high forest fire vulnerability, because in the forest, the seeds of the pine tree start to roll down when they catch fire due to their spherical shape, which leads to the spread of fire in the forest more quickly. Apart from this, there are some areas that are highly vulnerable to forest fire, which have moderate to low precipitation and very dense vegetation. They also have good road connectivity and settlement, which contribute to the occurrence of fire in forest.

Therefore, assessing the unique interplay of these forest fire affecting factors in such specific regions is essential for developing effective forest fire management strategies. Based on the map generated by the ANN model, the middle part of Almora, consisting of the whole Chaukhutiya, Someshwar, middle Dwarahat, and Ranikhet tehsil, is the most vulnerable to forest fires. In contrast, the southwestern part of Sult, northern Bhikiyasen, Bhanoli and Jainti

tehsil are less vulnerable to forest fires. This detailed mapping and assessment will help by applying targeted fire prevention and management efforts in the most vulnerable areas to effectively reduce the risk and impact of forest fires.

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Additional information

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.